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Azerbaijan-Türkiye: Strategic Cooperation in Science, Education and Culture

Abstract

This article analyzes the multifaceted cooperation between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Türkiye in the fields of science, education and culture. Based on common historical roots, language, religion and spiritual values, relations between the two fraternal states have significantly strengthened since the restoration of Azerbaijan's state independence in the late 20th century. The article emphasizes that Türkiye was the first country to recognize Azerbaijan's independence and provide it with comprehensive support, including in the humanitarian, scientific and educational spheres. Particular attention is paid to the development of scientific cooperation between academic and research institutions of both countries, student and faculty exchanges, implementation of joint projects, and holding international conferences. The article also discusses the main areas of cultural interaction, including joint celebrations, exhibitions, festivals, as well as cooperation in preserving cultural heritage and literary studies. The author concludes that deepening cooperation in these areas contributes not only to strengthening the national interests of Azerbaijan and Türkiye, but also to the development of a single cultural and spiritual space of the Turkic world.

Keywords: *Strategic Cooperation, Science, Education, Culture, Modern Era*

Azerbaycan-Türkiye: Bilim, Eğitim ve Kültür Alanlarında Stratejik İşbirliği

Öz

Bu makale, Azerbaycan Cumhuriyeti ile Türkiye Cumhuriyeti arasında bilim, eğitim ve kültür alanlarındaki çok yönlü işbirliğini analiz etmektedir. Ortak tarihi köklere, dile, dine ve manevi değerlere

dayanan iki kardeş devlet arasındaki ilişkiler, 20. yüzyılın sonlarında Azerbaycan'ın bağımsızlığını yeniden kazanmasından bu yana önemli ölçüde güçlenmiştir. Makalede, Türkiye'nin Azerbaycan'ın bağımsızlığını tanıyan ve insani, bilimsel ve eğitim alanları da dahil olmak üzere kapsamlı destek sağlayan ilk ülke olduğu vurgulanıyor. Her iki ülkenin akademik ve araştırma kurumları arasında bilimsel işbirliğinin geliştirilmesine, öğrenci ve öğretim üyesi değişimine, ortak projelerin uygulanmasına ve uluslararası konferansların düzenlenmesine özellikle dikkat çekiliyor. Makalede ayrıca ortak kutlamalar, sergiler, festivaller, kültürel mirasın korunması ve edebiyat çalışmalarında işbirliği de dahil olmak üzere kültürel etkileşimin ana alanları da tartışılmaktadır. Yazar, bu alanlarda işbirliğinin derinleştirilmesinin sadece Azerbaycan ve Türkiye'nin ulusal çıkarlarının güçlendirilmesine değil, aynı zamanda Türk dünyasının tek bir kültürel ve manevi alanının geliştirilmesine de katkıda bulunacağı sonucuna varmaktadır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Stratejik İşbirliği, Bilim, Eğitim, Kültür, Modern Çağ

Introduction

The relations between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Türkiye have deep historical roots, and the common language, religion, culture, history, and national-spiritual values have played a crucial role in the development of these relations. The brotherly ties between our nations are not limited to the modern era; they have withstood the test of centuries and have been evident in many historical events and struggles. The friendship and brotherhood formed between the peoples of both countries have been especially strengthened and elevated to the level of strategic partnership after the major political changes at the end of the 20th century—particularly following Azerbaijan's restoration of its state independence (Talyshinskiy El'vin Bakhrúz Ogly, 2021). One of the main directions of cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye is the development of mutual activity in the fields of science, education, and culture. The cultural and spiritual closeness, as well as the shared value systems of both countries, have created a favorable environment for the strengthening of this collaboration. After restoring its independence, Türkiye was the first country to recognize and support Azerbaijan's sovereignty. This fraternal support was not limited to the political arena but also manifested itself in science, education, and cultural fields. This has been particularly reflected in a number of joint programs and projects implemented since the 1990s.

Historically, Azerbaijan–Türkiye relations have developed since the Ottoman period, continuing in various forms during the early 20th century—particularly during the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic era—and later during the Soviet period. At the end of the 20th century, these relations entered a new phase, evolving into a broader form of cooperation between two independent states. In the post-independence period, relations in the fields of science, education, and culture between the two countries entered a qualitatively new stage, enriched by joint

projects, student exchanges, collaborative research among scholars, cultural events, and other activities.

As Hüseyinova (2018) noted, the development of cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye in the fields of science, education, and culture serves not only the interests of both states but also the integration of the Turkic world as a whole, as well as the preservation and advancement of shared values. This cooperation holds strategic importance for Azerbaijan not only in terms of gaining new knowledge and experience but also in terms of strengthening national and cultural identity, studying historical and cultural heritage, and promoting it on a global scale. Cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye in the fields of science, education, and culture is shaped not only through the efforts of state institutions and official bodies but also through the active involvement of public organizations, universities, research institutes, and cultural institutions. Within this framework, hundreds of young Azerbaijanis have received higher education in Türkiye, numerous scientists and experts have participated in joint projects, and many co-authored scientific articles, monographs, and research studies have been produced. This has contributed significantly to the strengthening of knowledge and experience exchange between the two countries.

In addition, significant progress has been made in the field of culture, creating opportunities for the peoples of both nations to become more closely acquainted through national holidays, cultural days, exhibitions, folklore festivals, and other events. As İsmayilov (2002) emphasizes, this cooperation is of great importance for preserving cultural diversity, promoting shared values, and passing them on to future generations.

As can be seen, cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye in the fields of science, education, and culture is not only a reflection of the current state of relations but also a fundamental component of their future development strategy. Strengthening these ties serves the national interests of both countries while also playing a crucial role in the advancement of pan-Turkic unity.

1. The Development of Scientific Cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye

Scientific cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye is mainly reflected in joint research conducted in fields such as history, linguistics, literature, cultural heritage, and others. Ferqane Hüseyinova (2018) emphasizes that after Azerbaijan regained its independence—particularly since the early 1990s—scientific relations entered a new phase. During this period, cooperation protocols were signed between the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences (ANAS) and various scientific research centers and universities in Türkiye, leading to the implementation of joint projects.

One of the most important directions of this scientific collaboration is research focused on shared history and cultural heritage. Altay Göyüşov (2010) notes that joint studies on topics such as Ottoman–Azerbaijani relations, Türkiye’s influence in the Caucasus region, and parallels in Azerbaijani and Ottoman literature are of particular significance. These studies have yielded results not only of academic value but also of interest to the general public.

At the same time, in the modern era, Azerbaijani and Turkish scholars are also conducting joint scientific research in areas such as information technologies, energy security, alternative energy sources, biodiversity, and environmental issues. According to Sevinc Ruinten (2005, p. 152), since the 2000s, scientific cooperation between Baku and Ankara has become more systematic, with numerous joint monographs and scholarly articles published on various scientific topics.

International conferences organized jointly by Azerbaijani and Turkish universities—such as “*Science and Culture in the Turkic World*” and “*Perspectives of Azerbaijan–Türkiye Scientific Cooperation*”—contribute to the expansion of collaboration in the field of science. These events not only serve as platforms for sharing scientific ideas but also play an important role in recognizing and supporting young researchers. İsmail İsmayilov (2002, p. 83) emphasizes that joint research conducted between Azerbaijan and Türkiye helps to strengthen the scientific potential of both countries and contributes to the formation of scientific unity across the Turkic world.

2. Expansion and Main Directions of Cooperation in the Field of Education

Cooperation in the field of education between Azerbaijan and Türkiye began to develop intensively, particularly from the early 1990s. As Ruinten Sevinj (2005, p. 144) writes, under the framework of the “Great Student Project” announced and implemented by Türkiye in 1992, thousands of Azerbaijani students were sent to study at Turkish higher education institutions. This project played an invaluable role in the restructuring of Azerbaijan’s education system and in increasing its pool of highly qualified professionals.

According to Ferqane Huseynova (2018, p. 59), currently, hundreds of Azerbaijani students are studying at various Turkish universities at the undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral levels. At the same time, Turkish students also have educational opportunities at universities in Azerbaijan. Student and faculty exchange has expanded through international programs such as dual diploma programs, Erasmus+, and the Mevlana Exchange Program.

Cooperation protocols and memorandums signed between Azerbaijani and Turkish universities—particularly between Baku State University, Azerbaijan University of Languages, Azerbaijan State University of Economics, and ADA University on one side, and Ankara

University, Istanbul University, Hacettepe University, and Ege University on the other—have significantly strengthened academic and educational collaboration.

In addition, joint projects in the field of education between Azerbaijan and Türkiye have led to the implementation of training programs focused on the professional development of teachers, curriculum reform, and the application of educational technologies. Seminars and training sessions conducted with the participation of experts from both countries have also played an important role in this regard.

Israfil Ismayilov (2002, p. 85) emphasizes that harmonizing the educational systems of Azerbaijan and Türkiye—particularly deepening cooperation in technical and vocational education—is among the priority directions for the future. At the same time, the preparation of specialists in the field of Turkish language and literature, the development of joint textbooks, and the establishment and advancement of Turkic World Research Centers are also key areas of this cooperation.

3. Main Directions and Initiatives in the Field of Culture

Cooperation in the field of culture between Azerbaijan and Türkiye is based on the historical roots, shared spiritual values, and cultural heritage of both nations. The expansion and sustainability of this cooperation is an essential component of the strategic partnership between the two countries. As Ferqane Huseynova (2018, p. 67) points out, Azerbaijan and Türkiye protect, enrich, and pass on their shared cultural heritage to future generations through cultural collaboration.

One of the main directions of cultural cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye is the joint celebration of national holidays and significant events. Organizing cultural events on important dates such as Novruz, Republic Day on May 28, and Independence Day on October 18 contributes to unity and solidarity between the two nations. At the same time, organizing Azerbaijan Culture Days in Türkiye and Türkiye Culture Days in Azerbaijan—as well as exhibitions, concerts, and theatrical performances—are key indicators of this cooperation.

Israfil Ismayilov (2004) notes that cultural cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye is particularly evident in the fields of music and the arts. Mugham and Turkish folk music are performed together in joint concerts; painting exhibitions, sculpture projects, film festivals, and folklore events serve to promote shared values between the two peoples.

Diaspora organizations and non-governmental organizations also play an important role in strengthening cultural relations between Azerbaijan and Türkiye. Azerbaijani diaspora organizations, cultural centers, and student unions operating in Türkiye make significant contributions to the promotion and dissemination of Azerbaijani culture through various events.

As Ruinten Sevinj (2005, p. 158) notes, cultural activities are not limited to the presentation of art and folklore but also include joint projects aimed at preserving and studying historical heritage. In addition, there is cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye in the restoration of cultural heritage monuments. Azerbaijani monuments in the city of Kars and Turkish monuments in Baku have become symbols of mutual respect and friendship.

One of the important aspects of cooperation is in the field of literature. Azerbaijani and Turkish literary scholars have jointly studied the works of both classical and contemporary poets and writers. In particular, academic articles, monographs, and translated works have been published on the literary legacy of great masters such as Nizami Ganjavi, Fuzuli, Muhammad Fuzuli, Yunus Emre, Ahmad Yasawi, Orhan Veli, Nazım Hikmet, and others. As Göyüşov Altay (2010) emphasizes, literary scholars from Azerbaijan and Türkiye hold joint conferences, prepare collaborative publications, and make significant contributions to the study and promotion of Turkic world literature.

Cooperation between the two countries in the field of cinema is also noteworthy. Joint films have been produced by Azerbaijani and Turkish directors, producers, and screenwriters, and documentaries have been made on topics related to shared history and culture. Films such as *“Karabakh – You Were Victorious!”* and *“Dear Azerbaijan”* have played an important role in presenting the realities of Azerbaijan to the international community (Ruinten, 2005).

Cooperation in book publishing also holds a significant place in Azerbaijani–Turkish cultural relations. As a result of agreements signed between publishing houses of both countries, samples of classical and contemporary Azerbaijani literature are published in Türkiye and made accessible to a wide readership, and Turkish literature is similarly promoted in Azerbaijan. For instance, during the “Azerbaijani Literature Days” held in Ankara in 2003, hundreds of Azerbaijani literary works were presented to Turkish readers (İsmayilov, 2004). Overall, cultural cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye not only strengthens the relationship between the two states but also contributes to the cultural integration of the entire Turkic world, the preservation of common values, and their transmission to future generations.

4. New Trends and Challenges in Cultural Cooperation

In the modern era, cultural cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye has entered a new phase. In the context of globalization, the development of technologies, digitalization, and the widespread use of new media tools have also influenced the forms and content of cultural collaboration. Huseynova Ferqane (2018) notes that cultural relations between the two countries are not limited to traditional events but also encompass new areas such as digital cultural products, electronic publications, online exhibitions, and virtual museum exhibits.

Azerbaijan and Türkiye implement joint cultural projects through digital platforms. For example, within the framework of the new cooperation memorandum signed in 2021 between the Ministry of Culture of Azerbaijan and the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of Türkiye, virtual cultural festivals and online conferences have been held. Cultural institutions, artists, and researchers from both countries actively participated in these projects, ensuring the continuity of cultural integration during the pandemic period (Ruinten, 2005). At the same time, one of the contemporary cultural challenges is the engagement of youth in cultural processes. Cooperation between higher education institutions, cultural centers, and youth organizations of Azerbaijan and Türkiye serves to unite young people around common values. Initiatives such as the “Turkic World Youth Forum,” the “Azerbaijan-Türkiye Youth Initiatives” project, student exchange programs, and cultural summer schools are important steps in this direction. Ismayilov Israfil (2002) emphasizes that Azerbaijani and Turkish youth, by participating in joint cultural projects, demonstrate their creative potential and contribute to the preservation and promotion of national and spiritual values.

However, there are also some challenges in cultural cooperation. Economic constraints, global crises such as the pandemic, unequal distribution of financial allocations to the cultural sector, technical and organizational difficulties in project implementation, and in some cases bureaucratic obstacles affect the continuity of activities in this field. Göyüşov Altay (2010) examines these issues and emphasizes that despite the existing difficulties, Azerbaijan and Türkiye are intensifying their efforts to deepen cooperation in the cultural sphere and constantly renewing cooperation formats in accordance with the challenges of the new era.

Additionally, the joint stance of Azerbaijan and Türkiye on international cultural platforms holds particular importance. Both countries work together within UNESCO, ICESCO, TÜRKSOY, and other international organizations, contributing to the promotion of Turkic culture, common values, and cultural heritage worldwide. Azerbaijan and Türkiye have taken significant steps towards the protection and promotion of shared heritage by preparing joint nomination dossiers for several monuments and intangible cultural heritage elements included in UNESCO’s “World Heritage List” (Hüseynova, 2018).

5. The Impact of Azerbaijan–Türkiye Cultural Relations on the Turkic World

Cultural cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye is not only significant within the framework of bilateral relations but also plays a crucial role in the cultural integration of the entire Turkic world. Since this cooperation is based on shared history and values, it greatly contributes to the better mutual understanding of cultures among Turkic peoples, deepening mutual relations, and the preservation of cultural heritage.

Ruinen Sevinj (2005) emphasizes that cultural cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye is one of the strategic means to strengthen unity among Turkic peoples. Joint projects, festivals, conferences, and exhibitions carried out within this cooperation framework have evolved into large-scale cultural events attended not only by Azerbaijan and Türkiye but also by Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and other Turkic states.

For example, the “Turkic World Capital of Culture” programs organized under TÜRKSOY have become a broad cultural platform covering a wider geography thanks to the initiatives of Azerbaijan and Türkiye. In 2019, the city of Shaki in Azerbaijan, and in 2022, the city of Bursa in Türkiye were awarded this status, becoming centers of Turkic world culture. Exhibitions, concerts, performances of folklore ensembles, joint book and article publications organized during these events have played an invaluable role in promoting Turkic cultural values (Hüseynova, 2018). Additionally, commemorating shared historical figures and events is also an important aspect of cultural cooperation. Anniversaries of great personalities such as Nizami Ganjavi, Yunus Emre, Fuzuli, Muhammad Fuzuli, Ahmed Yesevi, and others are celebrated jointly by Azerbaijan and Türkiye with the support of UNESCO and other international organizations. These events serve both to strengthen national consciousness and to present the richness of Turkic culture to the international community (İsmayilov, 2002, p. 94).

6. Perspectives and Future Plans of Cultural Cooperation

Cultural cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye also creates an important platform for the preservation and development of Turkic languages. Through joint language congresses, literary competitions, and linguistic conferences, collaborative efforts are made to develop a common Turkic vocabulary and to harmonize language and orthographic standards. Göyüşov Altay (2010) notes that Azerbaijani and Turkish scholars and cultural figures launch joint initiatives to strengthen their positions in the unified information space of the Turkic world, implementing joint television and radio projects.

The prospects for cultural cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye are quite broad. In the context of modern challenges, both countries aim to further develop the synthesis of technology and culture, carry out joint projects on digital platforms, and create shared cultural products using artificial intelligence and new media capabilities.

Ferqane (2018) emphasizes that among the future directions of cooperation, the most important are organizing large-scale joint cultural festivals, implementing joint projects in cinema and animation industries, and expanding exchange programs among young artists, composers, directors, and writers. At the same time, the creation of virtual museums,

digitization of joint archival materials, and making them accessible to the broader public are planned to protect and promote shared cultural heritage between Azerbaijan and Türkiye.

Moreover, cooperation between Azerbaijan and Türkiye in the restoration and revival of the cultural life of the Karabakh region holds special significance. Various cultural institutions and non-governmental organizations from Türkiye participate in restoring cultural centers in the territories of Azerbaijan freed from occupation, supporting the restoration of historical monuments and mosques. This contributes to strengthening the brotherly relations between the two countries (İsmayilov, 2004).

Conclusion

Cooperation between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Türkiye in the fields of science, education, and culture carries a multifaceted and strategic character in the modern era. Although the historical roots of this cooperation are based on common language, religion, culture, and history, new challenges, technological developments, and global processes in the contemporary period necessitate the deepening and enrichment of these relations. Research shows that scientific cooperation is mainly realized through joint project implementation, conducting scientific research, reciprocal visits of scientists and researchers, exchange of scientific publications, and co-organization of scientific conferences. Collaboration protocols signed between Azerbaijani and Turkish universities, joint master's and doctoral programs, especially joint initiatives in science and technology, strongly stimulate the development of scientific potential between the two countries. This cooperation also facilitates the training of young scientists and the preparation of internationally competitive specialists. Cooperation in the field of education has also expanded significantly and become one of the strategic priorities of both countries. Azerbaijani students studying in Türkiye, teacher and student exchange programs, joint educational projects, preparation of common educational materials, and efforts to teach the shared values of the Turkic world should be further deepened in the future. This process serves both the sharing of intellectual potential between the two countries and the preservation of the common historical and cultural heritage. Cultural cooperation is one of the most important pillars of the strategic partnership model between Azerbaijan and Türkiye. Organizing cultural events, literary and cultural connections, joint exhibitions, theater and cinema projects, music festivals, and art exchanges lay the foundation for strengthening brotherly and friendly relations between the peoples of the two countries. The activities carried out to promote the shared cultural heritage of Azerbaijan and Türkiye on a global scale, as well as joint initiatives within international organizations such as UNESCO and TÜRKSOY, play a special role in strengthening the cultural unity of the Turkic world.

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